

Spatial Relationship Criterion #4: Polygons In Polygons

The "Polygons In Polygons" spatial relationship criterion is useful for analyzing how certain polygon features are fully contained within others. For instance, it can determine which parcels of land fall entirely within specific zoning areas or help identify properties located completely within protected regions, like nature reserves or conservation zones.

In cadastral analysis, it can highlight smaller land parcels (such as subdivided lots) that fall entirely within larger municipal or administrative boundaries.

In our case, we have a cadastral dataset that includes both land parcels and building polygons. The building polygons represent all the buildings in the village, while the land parcels are only for a portion of the area, designated for specific use.

Our goal is to compare the two layers to see which buildings fall inside the designated land parcels and which ones, are located outside.

Let's get started;

Fig.1 The land parcels layer, consisting of multiple polygon features, and the buildings layer are successfully loaded into SGIS Desktop, ready for further analysis.

The land parcels layer, consisting of multiple polygon features, has been successfully loaded, along with the buildings layer.

Now, we'll open the 'Select by Layer' function. First, we click on the 'Selection Mode' dropdown to reveal the options, and we select "Polygons In Polygons".

Next, from the second dropdown list, we choose 'Buildings' as this is the layer we want to select features from.

Lastly, for the condition layer, we'll select the 'Land Parcels' layer. Since there are only two layers in the Layers panel, this choice is straightforward.

Fig.2 The 'Select by Layer' function is accessed, and the 'Selection Mode' dropdown reveals the available options. "Polygons In Polygons" is selected for the analysis.

Fig.3 The second dropdown menu is used to select the 'Buildings' layer, which contains the features to be analyzed and selected.

Fig.4 The 'Land Parcels' layer is selected from the dropdown as the condition layer for the spatial analysis.

Next, we click on 'Select' to continue with the process.

Fig.5 Clicking on the 'Select' button to execute the spatial selection process.

As shown in Fig.6, all building polygons that meet the criteria are immediately selected and highlighted.

Additionally, the selected elements are displayed in a tree-like list in the 'Selected Elements' panel.

Fig.6 Highlighted building polygons that meet the selection criteria, with corresponding elements listed in the 'Selected Elements' panel for easy navigation.

Fig.7 Zoomed-out view showing a few unselected buildings, which is correct since they do not meet the selection criteria, as they overlap with gaps or holes within a larger polygon.

An interesting detail in this case is that, as we zoom out, a few buildings remain unselected. This isn't an error. If we temporarily disable the Buildings layer from the Layers panel, we can see that these buildings don't meet the criteria because the areas they overlap aren't polygons, but gaps within a larger polygon.

Fig.8 After temporarily disabling the Buildings layer, the gaps within the larger polygon become visible, confirming that the unselected buildings are not within actual polygons but instead overlap empty spaces.

Fig. 9 Demonstrating the 'Pan to Element' function, where users can right-click on a selected element to automatically zoom in on its exact location and geometry in the graphics panel. Additionally, options to expand or collapse tree items, remove elements from the selection, or export an element's ID are available for further functionality.

We can select an element from the Selected Elements list, right-click on it, and choose 'Pan to Element'. This will take us directly to that specific element, highlighting its geometry and location.

There are additional options, such as expanding or collapsing the tree items, removing an element from the selection, or exporting the element's ID as a text file.

For demonstration purposes, we'll now move ahead and use the 'Unselected Elements in New Layer' function. This will create a new layer in the Layers panel, containing all elements that were not part of the previous selection process.

Fig. 10 Demonstrating the use of the 'Unselected Elements in New Layer' function, which generates a new layer in the Layers panel, containing all elements that were not selected in the previous spatial query.

Fig. 11 The newly created layer, displayed in the attribute table, contains 428 building polygons. The Info bar at the bottom-right corner confirms 225 selected elements from the process, representing the building polygons that overlap with land parcels.

As shown, the new layer is created instantly. Upon opening the attribute table, we can see that this layer contains 428 elements, or building polygons. The Info bar in

the bottom-right corner shows the number of selected elements from our process— 225 building polygons.

If we compare this to the original buildings layer, which contains 653 building polygons, the numbers align perfectly. We selected 225 polygons that overlap with land parcels, while 428 polygons did not meet that criterion.

With this, we successfully complete the procedure.

Fig.12 The original buildings layer holds 653 polygons in total, confirming the accuracy of the process. This completes the procedure.